

Creation of Admin Modules and Design of Application Databases Exercise National Standard School End Test

Admin Modules and Design of Application Database

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National Standard School End Test (UASBN) as a form of assessment of learning outcomes by the government which became the benchmark of the success of elementary school students in following the learning process in school. The purpose of UASBN is to know and measure the level of mastery of certain subject matter nationally. using prototype method consist of communication, quilk plan, quick design, prototype construction and delivery a feed back. the goal is to know the readiness of the students before the exam. make the parents know the development of his son. Her conclusion is this application helps the students improve their ability in facing exams.

Keywords: System, Application, Exercise Problem, Exercise, LCG, Final School Exam, Application, System, Problem, UAS.

1. INTRODUCTION

National Standard School End Test (UASBN) as a form of assessment of learning outcomes by the government that became the benchmark of the success of primary school students in following the process of learning in school. The purpose of UASBN is to know and measure the level of mastery of certain subject matter nationally. Similarly, National Examination according to Permendikbud of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 Year 2003 article 1 about graduation criteria learners from education unit and implementation of examination of school / madrasah / equivalency education and national examination states that "National Examination hereinafter referred to as UN is measurement and measurement national graduate competence on certain subjects in science and Mathematics subject groups Having good UASBN results gives them the widest possible opportunity to pursue higher education or Junior High School. Various steps done by the school supported by related parties to prepare students in facing the UN in order to provide maximum results (Gultom Syawal, 2012).

The value of Try Out as a benchmark to see students' ability to deal with UASBN. Try Out is one form of evaluation conducted by schools and related parties to prepare students

face UASBN. The UASBN tryout is formulated through careful consideration in order to represent the questions to be tested at UASBN. Hope from the school and students that the results try out UASBN can describe the UASBN results to be achieved by students. In addition, try out is also conducted to see the level of ability and readiness of students in following UASBN (Gultom Syawal, 2012).

Therefore designed a system that can be a means for students Sekoah Basic in the face of the National Standard School End Test (UASBN). Equipped with an online-based problem-based feature, students can also download examples of the latest National Standard School End Test available on the Bank Problem feature.

2. METHODOLOGY

The author uses the approach of System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) Prototype model in its development. Use Prototyping method because this method provides regular SDLC according to system requirement that writer design. Here are the steps in using the prototype method:

1. Needs collection

Here is the method of collecting needs done by the author:

- Read the literature as a guide to start the thesis.
- Make a letter requesting data to the education office to get the problem of previous UN.
- Identify and analyze the needs already obtained.

2. Quick Design

System design is done by describing the flow using UML so the system is well planned.

3. Build Prototype

After getting the model of manufacture, the author began to make prototype which will be conceived to the supervisor lecturer.

4. Evaluation of Prototype

At this stage, the authors perform testing by using alpha test to determine the success of the system that has been made.

5. Repair Prototype

At this stage the system that has been tested will be mendbaiki and the author again see the reference before doing guidance to the lecturer.

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